

A NOTE ON THE ACTION OF THE CHLORINE-BLEACH ON THE RESIN CONSTITUENTS OF LAC.

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A study of the chemical changes undergone by the resin constituents of lac during bleaching with hypochlorite solution has been made.

Bleaching is accompanied by an increase in the acid value and an apparent increase in the saponification value and ester value of lac. On making due allowance for the reaction between the chlorine present in bleached lac and the alcoholic potash used in saponification, real saponification and ester values can be calculated. The real (or corrected) saponification value of shellac is about 5% higher than that of unbleached lac, thus indicating an increase in the carboxyl groups due to oxidative changes brought about by the chlorine bleach. Aleuritic acid, a constituent of lac, does not appear to have been affected by the chlorine-bleach. The hydroxyl number generally decreases slightly on bleaching.

Chlorine enters into the resin molecules, and its content increases steadily as the lac is progressively bleached, while the iodine value decreases rapidly in the beginning and then tends to attain a minimum value. The chlorine in bleached lac exists only partly as an addition compound the excess entering the molecule through substitution. The chemical changes, *viz.*, oxidation and chlorination, are brought about in the resin molecules almost immediately after the addition of the bleaching agent. But the changes in the colouring matter, although proceeding simultaneously, take some time to attain completion. The rate of absorption of bleach is quicker in poor bleaching lacs than in good Kusum lac and is further enhanced by employing a higher temperature and lower p_H .

When bleached lac is allowed to remain in the alkaline solution after all the added hypochlorite has been consumed, the following changes take place, the extent of these changes depending upon the duration, temperature and p_H .

(a) The chlorine content decreases, the unsaturation increases due to splitting off of hydrochloric acid and the colour of the bleached lac tends to return.

(b) The acid value increases due to hydrolysis, consequently the ester value decreases.

(c) The saponification value appears to decrease slightly due probably to the splitting off of carbon dioxide from the carboxyl groups or due to removal of some acid constituent of lower molecular weight during washing.

A slower rate of attack on the resin molecules by a gradual addition of the bleaching liquor gives a product which is less prone to become insoluble than a rapidly bleached product. Higher alkalinity of the bleaching liquor and other conditions which bring about hydrolysis give a bleached lac which will have a longer life, but which will have the disadvantage of high acid value and poor colour.

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